

Energy, Nuclear Energy, Alternatives, Politics: A Critical Wholeness Analysis

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Abstract

A comprehensive analysis, with respect to energy, nuclear energy, and alternative energy resources on the technical and political level is presented. A sound utopia based on the imitation of natural cycles that have given birth to mankind on Earth, is drawn.

Keywords: Alternative Energy resources, Bad, Chernobyl, Cosmic Wholeness, Energy, Energy Ethics, Good, Nuclear Energy, World Politics.

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1. Introduction

“World nuclear capacity growth”, actually exhibits an “open S curve”. This is just like the “(age / height) curve” of a tree². [1-3]

This is true not only as a whole, but in general, for all of various countries which had gone the nuclear way.

Figure 1. Nuclear Energy Debate in the Past and in the Present" [in Turkish: 1st Edition 1995 (Esin Yayınevi, Second Edition 2010 (Okan University), Third Edition 2014 (Okan University), ISBN 9786055899127. [3, 4]

² This manuscript is made out of the text of the invited talk delivered by the author in the *International Chernobyl Seminar*, held between, April 23rd and 26th, 2000, in Ceremo, Kiev, Ukraina. The text was revised in July 2013. The talk was based on the author's book, "*Debate on Nuclear Energy in the Past and Nowadays*", first published by Esin Yayınevi, in 1995, then by Okan University in 2010 and 2014, in Istanbul.

2. How Did Nuclear Power Deployment Grow?

So, there was a rather “fast growth” chiefly, after 1970’s, then a “saturation”, after mid 1980’s.

There are two basic reasons for the fast growth. The first one is that, originally, nuclear energy was discovered to be very attractive.

With about one ton of uranium 235, one can produce the same amount of electricity that a 1000 MWelectric giant dam would produce through an entire year period. This is plenty of energy in a very dense form. This energy, on the other hand, seemed very abundant, with no obvious or unsolvable problems. The abundance of uranium 235 in natural uranium, being little less than 1%, one needs little more than 100 tons of natural uranium to tap the energy just mentioned.

So, at 1960’s, nuclear energy production technology appeared to be cheap, environmentally clean, and safe, as compared to basically coal fired energy production. The latter posed indeed several difficulties and impediments, from coal mining to the leftovers and sulfur and nitrogen gases production, which ultimately, turn out to be the unbearable acid rains.

The second reason for which nuclear energy production has gone fast after 1970’s is that, Western European countries were poor in regards to energy resources. Consequently, they were dependent on import oil, mainly from Middle Eastern Countries. But during the cold war, Middle East has always been a shaky place. (In many ways, it still is, and nowadays it surely is.) This necessitated decreasing the import oil dependency. Even the USA who possessed rather rich oil resources followed the strategy of “draining OPEC oil first”. The first oil crisis in 1973 backed up the need of decreasing dependency on oil.

These are the basic reasons for which nuclear power production was highly favored in the Western Countries, and likewise the Eastern Block, by then, led by the Soviet Union.

The second oil crisis came into the world scene in 1979. The oil price went up tremendously, to reach the ceiling of 30 and even 35 dollars per barrel.

Recall that it was 3 dollars per barrel in 1973, and it became 8 dollars per barrel after the 1973 oil crisis.

The western economies were shaken even more through the second oil crisis of 1979. This yielded an outmost expectation from nuclear energy.

This yielded also a scientific and technological meditation in the entire world about our consumption fashions of energy as well as the development of other energy resources.

And here, a totally unexpected energy resource was discovered. This is “conservation of energy”, or in better terms, “energy efficiency”.

The entire world, starting by the USA and the Western Europe, indeed surprisingly discovered that we can do everything that we used to do by using only half of the energy we previously had to use (and in very many cases even less)! This is surely striking, and a shame regarding our previous energy consumption tendencies.

Hence, the demand projections came down tremendously. One thus realized that we did not need so much energy, or so much nuclear power production. This made that, so far, the world had only achieved 10% of the nuclear power capacity, which was planned for today, from the mid 1970's.

3. How Did Nuclear Power Production did Lose Its Popularity?

From here on, there are two basic reasons for which nuclear power production lost its popularity and came to its actual rather saturated production level. The first one embodies totally unexpected and utterly savage nuclear accidents. Along this line, we should basically recall the Three Mile Island (TMI) accident taken place in 1979 in the USA, and then, the much more severe Chernobyl accident taken place in 1986, in the Soviet Union. Fundamentally, the second accident destroyed very much the trust, people had for nuclear power production. The totally unexpected Fukushima accident that took place in 2011 did even more in destroying the “good image” of nuclear power production. “Small” accidents, as far as the end effects are concerned, such as the Tokai-Mura fuel plant accident, surely did not add less to the trust destruction of the world public to nuclear power production. It should be stressed that, all of TMI,

Chernobyl and Fukushima accidents (as much as the Tokai-Mura accident), had occurred for entirely unexpected reasons. No scenario could have predicted the funny paths these accidents delineated. The occurrences in question, gradually, required more and more redundant safety measures developments which led to the eradicating of the economic advantages of nuclear energy production. The nuclear economy situation was worsened by expenditures implied by the decommissioning of nuclear power plants, which were badly underestimated, at the beginning of nuclear era.

The second reason for which the world experiences nuclear power production saturation is, the problem posed by nuclear wastes. There are proposed solutions but they are not yet publically accepted, so that the waste problem, as it stands now, not only is “unresolved” but also, it ruins more the economy of nuclear power, since it drains much more financial resources than it was originally guessed.

Thus, nuclear power production, as, at least by now half of the Europeans perceive it, is neither cheap, nor clean, nor safe. The fact that many scientists and technocrats believe the other way around, does not change the profile of the perception in question; quite on the contrary the number of the opponents of nuclear energy increased day by day.

Nuclear energy, no doubt, has achieved a lot. It actually does achieve a lot, amounting to about one fifth of the world electricity production.

Yet, there are reasons to believe that nuclear energy is already in crisis. The open S curve related to its growth tells us that, it is somewhat at the end of its life time. There are exceptions, mainly the Republic of China, which envisages an ambitious nuclear program. There are not any new constructions in the USA since 1978; few nuclear entrepreneurships raise only nowadays; there are not any plants in OECD countries planned for the coming years; Sweden, Germany, Austria and Italy have chosen throughout democratic processes not to go nuclear or to abandon nuclear; Spain, Switzerland and Belgium consider seriously to get off the nuclear track; on the other hand we should recall that, from the beginning up to now, Ireland, Denmark, Holland, Portugal, Poland and Norway had never chosen to go the nuclear way.

So, on the whole, nuclear energy production, seemingly, appears to be in crisis.

One cannot talk about energy or nuclear energy without talking about politics; unfortunately sometimes about dirty politics and, even more unfortunately, about bloody politics. It is a pity that some of the scientists and technocrats, naively believe that our choices come only out of scientific laboratories, mathematical formulations and solutions, and computer outputs.

This is not the case at all. The choice of energy is in fact just a political choice not any different than that of a political party. As a matter of fact, our energy customs, just like our other daily customs, are determined and imposed by world politics and world lords. No world lord can be thought of without a political party or, in general, a political power.

Nuclear energy seems anyway a dead end business, if the world cannot go breeding nuclear fuel, mainly plutonium. The reason is a simple. Uranium resources are limited to about 6 million tons, just like oil, gas and coal resources are limited. And about one fifth of these resources are already depleted.

The world uranium resources can fuel the present reactors for only about half a century.

On the other hand, petroleum and natural gas resources of Earth seem to be much more voluminous than they were thought to be. So are coal resources.

4. Inacceptable Alternatives

When one thinks about the alternatives, one should not restrain himself to global figures. One instead should approach to the problem by local means. For instance, tidal energy may indeed be important for France and England, but not at all important for Turkey and Greece. These countries do not even have practically any tides. Conversely solar power may not be very important for Finland, but it should be considered to be very important for Mediterranean Countries.

Energy production means that are not compatible with the natural cycles of Earth shall probably be classified to be not acceptable in the long run. Thus, neither coal, nor petroleum, nor gas, are acceptable. They all alter the composition of our atmosphere. From this angle, nuclear energy too shall be in the long run classified as inacceptable, not only because

of the accident risks, but most likely, because of nuclear waste problem.

From this point of view, only solar energy, wind energy, tidal energy, biomass energy, and derivatives, such as hydrogen energy, shall stand in different forms of production in the long run.

NASA, already in 1979 reported that it could provide Earth, day and light with solar energy, via means of solar panels to be installed in space. But, of course, world politics did not so far allow such an excursion.

The reason forwarded by the opponents, is that it would be “very expensive”, i.e. about 1000 billion dollars, for a first serious space solar energy harnessing step, aimed to replace nuclear energy production. Yet the world “defense” expenditures, on a yearly basis, already amounts to this price.

5. Conclusion

All we have to do is to switch our mentality.

We have to learn how to live without fighting, if this ought to turn out to be the price of enjoying living healthily on this beautiful planet.

Hence one should politically fight to achieve the desirable energy solutions, just like chiefly Democrat Europeans had to fight for no more nuclear weapons in Europe.

If we pollute, it is either because we do not use the right energy resources, or we do not use them in the right way.

On Earth, we can continuously build “order”, and this, without any natural destruction, because Earth is an “open system”; we receive plenty of energy from the sun.

Since we pollute and since chaos is spread, this means that we are not, on the right track.

The entire world industry, as well as the civilization, mankind has developed on Earth, ought to be questioned from this point of view.

Anyhow, we have to be realistic, in the related transformation actions. This bears not an easy solution.

It is important to understand our creation on Earth, and before this, the cosmic struggles that gave birth

to Earth. It is as if, an unconscious consciousness is getting more and more ordered to become our conscious reaching our level of life.

I believe, it is important to get aligned with this cosmic self-organizing process and to pick it up, as our mission on Earth.

Anything we achieve in this line can be defined as “good”. Anything we achieve in an incompatibility with this line is then “bad”.

We can call this, our “cosmic wholeness”.

To be just “antinuclear” is not good enough, if it does not take place under the umbrella of our cosmic wholeness, out of which we can possibly derive a complete ethic system to shape up our daily life and our civilization. To shape up our energy production fashion, can simply be considered as a subset of such an approach.

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